

A Human-Centred Approach to the Design and Evaluation of Automotive Seat Adjustment Controls

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Abstract

This paper considers the design of seat adjustment controls in the premium sports utility vehicle sector, and takes a human-centred approach to collecting both positive and negative data regarding existing controls on a number of vehicles. The research draws on sensory science techniques and attempts to apply them in an automotive engineering arena, addressing in particular affective elements of seat adjustment control design. To achieve this, a one-hundred participant customer clinic event was held, with additional data sourced from an industry-standard, commercial survey. The data sets are analysed and compared in order to draw conclusions and make design recommendations relating to the functional and emotional aspects of seat adjustment control design. The findings from this research identify key factors resulting in both positive and negative user experiences for the vehicles selected for the study. In addition, comparisons with, and limitations of, commercial survey data are explored.

Conference theme: Usage and Interaction

Keywords: Seat Adjustment Controls, Affective Design, Content Analysis

Introduction

Travelling in a car is no longer simply about getting from A to B. It can be about excitement or relaxation, information or entertainment. As the role of the car in everyday life becomes more complex, so too does understanding the wants, needs and priorities of the customer, with regard to interaction with the vehicle. The influx of technologies into the average car has significantly raised the importance of the human machine interfaces within it, as it is the design of these interfaces that ultimately determines whether or not customer can take full advantage of the technologies presented and contribute to associated positive or negative emotional experiences.

Research has regularly highlighted the importance of incorporating customer input into the design of new products, throughout new product development, whether in the automotive or other transportation sectors, or consumer products in general (Campbell et al, 2007; Margolin, 1997). Automotive OEMs in particular face the dichotomy that, whilst customers demand access to the latest technologies, they also want simple, intuitive user controls, in-keeping with the vehicle interior styling and overall brand image. Additionally, the design of automotive user controls must address the safety concerns associated with potential distraction from the task of driving (Board and Stevens, 2001; Stevens, 2000). Hence, designing automotive HMI presents complex challenges and requires considerable user-centred research if optimal solutions are to be achieved.

Desmet and Hekkert (2007) describe how user-centred design is evolving from the study of behaviour, to encompass the overall affective experience resulting from human product interaction. Japanese manufacturers have led the automotive industry in this respect, through Kansei engineering, which focuses on the relationship between the properties of a product and the experience of interacting with it, and Quality Function Deployment (QFD) which links customer wants to design attributes and product parameters (Wellings et al, 2008). Today, premium automotive manufacturers recognise the importance of these methods as they strive to differentiate their products and gain competitive advantage in an increasingly crowded marketplace. Furthermore, the concept of ‘designing for the senses’, as described by MacDonald (2001), is becoming recognised as a means of improving the user’s overall emotional experience through interaction with the vehicle controls.

Applying the appropriate methods, however, is complex and the collaborative research described in this paper seeks to collect and analyse appropriate data to enable an affective approach to the design of seat adjustment controls for premium sports utility vehicles (SUVs).

The research described is part of a £800,000 EPSRC funded Innovative Manufacturing Research Centre (IMRC) project at WMG, within the University of Warwick, addressing future human machine interface (HMI) needs of the automotive industry. This project builds on the success of a four year, £33M regional development agency funded, industry-focused R&D programme, within which this project team's remit was to improve craftsmanship-related capabilities of the UK's premium automotive industry. The project team has a strong background in user control haptics and the capture and analysis of 'voice of the customer' data in automotive new product development, with a number of publications in this and related fields.

Research Methodology and Sources of Data

The theme and scope of the research described were derived from discussions between WMG, a premium vehicle manufacturer and a first tier supplier of seating systems for premium sector vehicles. As is common in the automotive industry, commercial survey data (J. D. Power and Associates, 2006) highlighted areas of customer dissatisfaction, and the vehicle manufacturer and their supplier were trying to decipher these data in order to determine and prioritise necessary design changes. The high-level nature of this survey data tends to be good for identifying where there are problems, but less good for understanding underlying causes, and this resulted in a need for more detailed data to confirm the survey data and explore in greater depth the relationship between the user and seat adjustment controls, and the emotions evoked by the process of interaction.

A customer clinic event was, therefore, designed and run by the University of Warwick, which brought together six premium SUVs and 100 participants – owners or principle drivers of vehicles in that segment (predominantly the specific vehicles chosen for the study), over a two day period. The event was run in the UK at a neutral venue, and all participants were UK residents. Participants assessed various aspects of the seat adjustment controls of six selected premium SUVs, in context, whilst seated in the drivers' seat.

The vehicles were positioned around the edge of the venue, allowing unrestricted access to the front seats, as illustrated in Figure 1. The six vehicles selected were a BMW X5, Mercedes M-Class, Porsche Cayenne, Range Rover Sport, Volvo XC90 and Lexus RX350

Figure 1 – Vehicles at the clinic venue

The vehicles had fully or partially electrically operated seat adjustment controls. The seat adjustment controls for each of these six vehicles are illustrated below in Figure 2:

BMW X5

Volvo XC90

Porsche Cayenne

Range Rover Sport

Lexus RX350

Mercedes M Class

Figure 2 – Seat adjustment controls on the drivers' seat of the six vehicles

Participants were first asked to try out the seat adjustment controls in each of the vehicles in order to familiarise themselves with the different functions and control layouts, and to experience the full range of controls to be assessed. Following this familiarisation, the participants were given a questionnaire and asked to follow the instructions, assessing the vehicles one at a time, in a random order. Participants were instructed to close the drivers' door before commencing each assessment and this controlling factor was imposed in order to (a) make participants' contextual experience of operating the seat adjustment controls as similar as possible, and (b) replicate a 'worst case scenario' whereby the user is unable to use visual cues to assist in understanding and operating controls. No attempt was made to disguise the brand or model of the vehicles being assessed as most participants would be familiar with at least one of the vehicles. A final caveat was introduced, asking participants not to discuss their findings or opinions with one another whilst familiarising themselves with controls or performing assessments.

Data were gathered by self administered questionnaire, due to the high number of participants, limited time available and relatively broad subject area. The yes/no, 'tick in box' approach of the J. D. Power and Associates surveys was avoided wherever possible through the use of rating scales, most/least preferred and open ended questions which encouraged both positive and negative emotional responses/comments. These responses were then subjected to a content analysis to identify and quantify trends in responses across the group of participants, with the more quantitative responses (ratings and most/least preferred) providing a preference-based reference against which the results of the content analysis could be compared, based on an approach advocated by Kassirjian (1977).

The questionnaire was comprised of two sections. The first of which required the participant to rate specific aspects of each vehicle individually, and the second required the participant to rank the six vehicles against a set of criteria and to give overall opinions not specific to any one vehicle. Further details of the specific questions whose answers have been analysed and presented in this paper, are given the Data Analysis and Findings section.

No assumptions were made regarding the importance of particular controls or functions, and participants were allowed to choose which areas of the seating system they would comment on. These unguided responses are analysed to determine importance and priorities relating to the various aspects of the seat adjustment controls, and from this, specific controls and functions could be selected for future study in greater detail. Further comments on the data collection method employed and recommendations for future studies are discussed later in the paper.

Data Analysis and Findings

With the range of data collected, particularly the quantitative information from the customer clinic, there are a number of different aspects of seat adjustment that could be addressed, and methods that could be applied. To understand affective aspects of user interaction with seat adjustment controls, the analysis is deliberately kept to a high level, with only limited consideration of specific controls/functions, but still relates closely to J. D. Power and Associates (2006) data - the point of reference for this investigation, and which holds considerable weight within the industry. For the purpose of this paper, areas of focus will include an investigation of the most common positive and negative responses from the customer clinic, and a case study looking at data relating to a specific aspect of seat adjustment controls.

Content analysis of qualitative customer clinic data

The following three open-ended questions were asked in the first section of the questionnaire, giving a total of 1366 comments, relating to the seating systems of the individual vehicles from the 100 participants of the clinic.

1. When operating the seat adjustment controls, did you find any aspect particularly pleasing, and why?
2. When operating the seat adjustment controls, did you find any aspect particularly difficult to use or understand, and why?
3. Do you have any further comments regarding the seat adjustment controls on this vehicle?

Initial inspection of the data revealed that the comments could not simply be separated and analysed by question as, whilst some participants were careful to answer the specific questions asked, in particular, the “difficult to use or understand” question, some participants took this as a cue to give more general negative comments. The data were, therefore, first divided into positive and negative categories, giving 737 positive and 629 negative comments.

The *content analysis* technique was then used to explore further the meaning of the comments and for this purpose, 29 positive and 29 negative categories were derived from the data and clear coding instructions were defined to maximise the reliability of the analysis (Krippendorff, 2004). Responses to each question were separated into discrete statements, which were then assigned to one of the pre-determined categories. The relative importance of a category is determined by the number of comments attributed to it. Results from this analysis are shown in Figures 3 and 4.

Figure 3 – Most frequent positive comments relating to the seat adjustment controls

Figure 4 – Most frequent negative comments relating to the seat adjustment controls

From Figure 3 it can be seen that the most important category for positive responses is ‘ease of use’, attracting over twice the number of comments of the second category ‘general praise’. ‘Accessibility’ features as the third category. A similar pattern appears in Figure 4 for negative comments, with ‘accessibility’ attracting significantly more comments than other categories.

The second most important category for negative responses is ‘ease of use’. Whilst ‘accessibility’ is relatively straightforward to classify, the term ‘ease of use’ encompasses a number of aspects of seat adjustment. Typical ‘ease of use’ comments include:

- “Easy to operate” (positive)
- “Intuitive” (positive)
- “Simple to understand” (positive)
- “...took a while to work out” (negative)
- “...hard to adjust” (negative)

Breaking the data down further revealed that, whilst the positive ‘ease of use’ comments were shared relatively evenly across the six vehicles, the BMW and, in particular, the Mercedes received noticeably more negative comments than the other vehicles, see Figure 5. In the case of the Mercedes, a significant proportion of these negative comments targeted the seat memory controls.

Figure 5 – Ease of use comments, broken down by vehicle

The spread of accessibility-related comments, in particular the negative one, were less evenly shared between vehicles, see Figure 6, with the Range Rover Sport attracting significantly more negative comments than its nearest rival. As might be expected from this category (with the seat adjustment controls of most of the vehicles as a cluster), negative accessibility comments typically related to the seat adjustment controls as a whole.

Figure 6 – Accessibility comments, broken down by vehicle

With over sixty negative comments relating to the accessibility of the seat adjustment controls of the Range Rover Sport, it was possible to perform a deeper analysis of these specific responses whilst maintaining a good degree of confidence in the results. This further analysis revealed 30 comments relating directly to the positioning of the arm rest on the door casing impeding access to the seat adjustment controls, with further comments similarly relating to the ‘door moulding’, ‘door panel’, ‘door trim’ and ‘door’ all causing a similar problem.

In addition to these quantitative findings, it was also observed from the comments that, whilst the positive ‘ease of use’ comments were numerous, few conveyed any obvious emotions of the participant. On the other hand, negative comments relating to accessibility, particularly those associated with the Range Rover Sport, often portrayed clear signs of annoyance and frustration. For example:

“Access difficult and actually hurts!”

“Found I could trap my hand between door grab handle and seat side - did not like it at all”

“Because of the arm rest position in relation to the seat controls, I would need a second wrist fitted between wrist and elbow”

Case study on seat memory controls

A specific area highlighted by J. D. Power and Associates (2006) as causing significant customer dissatisfaction is that of seat memory controls. Comments relating to this function/control have been analysed and a case study performed on seat memory controls, which

happened to be the most common category when analysing the customer clinic data by control/function.

Taking comments relating to the seat memory controls and breaking them down by type of comment and vehicle*, yielded the results shown in Table 1.

Category	Vehicle					Grand Total
	Lexus	BMW	Mercedes	RR Sport	Volvo	
+ Ease of Use		1	2		1	4
+ Location	3		1			4
+ Accessibility					2	2
+ Easy to find			1	1		2
+ Feel		1				1
+ Functional aspects			1			1
General Praise				1		1
Positive Total	3	2	5	2	3	15
- Ease of Use	1	5	11	1	5	23
- Difficult to Find	4		5	10	1	20
- Functional aspects					1	1
- Accessibility		1		3		4
- Feel			2		1	3
- General Criticism			2			2
- Location	1	1				2
- Layout			2			2
- Fiddly					1	1
Negative Total	6	7	22	14	9	58
Grand Total	9	9	27	16	12	73

Table 1 – Breakdown of seat memory control comments for each vehicle

* The Porsche Cayenne has been omitted as it did not have seat memory controls.

As can be seen from Table 1, there were significantly more negative than positive comments relating to seat memory controls, with a large proportion relating to ‘ease of use’ and ‘difficult to find’. Nearly half of the ‘ease of use’ comments related to the Mercedes, whilst exactly half of the ‘difficult to find’ comments related to the Range Rover Sport.

Examples of the negative ‘ease of use’ comments for the Mercedes include:

“Memory switches are difficult to operate, locate and figure out”

“Quite difficult to pick which pre-set position switch to select”

Examples of the negative ‘difficult to find’ comments for the Range Rover Sport include:

“Pre-set positions impossible to identify when in driver's seat”

“Cannot see buttons so makes it a little hard to use the memory buttons and difficult to find”

“Had to open door to find memory”

There is an identifiable theme to the ‘difficult to find’ and ‘ease of use’ comments, for all the vehicles with seat memory controls located on the side of the seat with other adjustment controls, which refers to a desire, but inability, to see these particular controls when trying to find and operate them. Of the five vehicles with such controls, only the Lexus had them positioned away from other seat adjustment controls, on the driver’s door trim, where they are visible to the user. It is interesting that three of the participants gave positive comments regarding location of the memory controls, however, four of the participants thought they were ‘difficult to find’.

Discussion

The design and location of seat adjustment controls presents an unusual challenge to the automotive designer. Most user controls within a car are visible to the user and within easy reach, making them easy to find, understand and use. They fit in with their surroundings and look and feel like high quality, expensive components. Seat adjustment controls have, traditionally, been located on the side of the seat base. Their appearance is not critical to interior styling and they are highly functional, but despite this, research described in this paper demonstrates that they can evoke strong, often negative, emotions in the user. So how can the automotive designer optimise the design of seat adjustment controls to improve the user experience?

From the customer clinic event, certain conclusions and hypotheses can be drawn from analysis of the data, which could serve as ‘guidelines’ to designers and engineers responsible for automotive seating systems (and interior systems integration).

The holistic approach taken to the evaluation of the seat adjustment controls, as illustrated in Figures 3 and 4, indicates the significant factors that influence affective responses such as pleasure and dissatisfaction. Although the most common responses, positive and negative, are predominantly linked to ease of use and accessibility, comments relating to these ‘operational’ categories still convey emotion, particularly the negative comments, where annoyance and frustration are evident in a number of the participants. This implies that ‘accessibility’ in particular, is a *must have* attribute for seat adjustment controls - the customer expects an acceptable level of performance from the product and shows strong dissatisfaction when this is

not delivered. Based on the number of negative responses that also relate to obstruction by the arm rest, door trim and door bin, it can be concluded that it is not simply the design and positioning of the seat adjustment controls that elicit these responses, but also the design and proximity of the door trim and associated components that contribute to the user's emotional experience of interacting with the controls in question.

The results from this research clearly suggest that there is a relationship between usability and the emotions evoked in the participants of the study. In particular, poor usability, encompassing accessibility and intuitiveness of operation, was a significant cause of negative emotions, such as frustration and annoyance. Similar findings resulted from a study on automotive centre console switchgear by Wellings *et al* (2008), who found that characteristics including size, layout and spacing (which are strongly related to usability) were all important factors contributing to both positive and negative emotional responses from the study participants. It could, therefore, be concluded that usability should be a key consideration in the design of HMI in automotive environments, and it would be logical to hypothesise that, across many fields of design, providing good usability to the customer is likely to result in a positive experience and, perhaps more importantly, sub-standard usability is particularly likely to evoke negative emotions.

From the case study, it is observed that clinic participants gave very few positive responses relating specifically to the seat memory controls, but there was a number of negative comments regarding accessibility and ease of use. There is a fundamental difference between the controls that operate the seat motors (directly moving the base, back and headrest), and the memory settings, in that the motor controls can be arranged intuitively in the general shape of the seat (with an obvious and separate base and back control – see Figure 2). Thus, through touch alone, a user can relatively quickly work out the basic functions. Memory controls are a different matter and, although the simplest symbols can suffice if buttons are visible, if not, the sense of touch alone would appear not to differentiate between (typically) three non-descript setting buttons and a 'set' button. Certain manufacturers (notably Mercedes – Figure 2) have attempted to improve this situation by changing the layout of the buttons and by adding raised 'pips' denoting settings one, two and three. No data from this study would suggest, however, that these modifications have resulted in functional or emotional improvements.

There was a mixed (and limited) response to the alternative location of memory controls on the Lexus, see Table 1, from which no strong conclusions can be drawn. This is, however, clearly an area that would benefit from a more detailed study.

A limitation of the customer clinic was that, whilst the participants owned a vehicle within the premium SUV segment, for a high percentage of the study, a participant is placed in an unfamiliar vehicle and asked to find/operate a function (the location of which they probably don't know). This may lead to an initial negative reaction which, over time, might evolve into a positive one if the participant were to become more familiar with the controls. This type of study is only likely to capture the initial reaction, unless the participant owns that particular vehicle. To capture longer term emotional reactions to the various aspects of seat adjustment controls, an alternative data capture method would be required, focusing on drivers of specific vehicles after a certain period of ownership.

Commercial survey data fulfils this criterion and is likely to be a good source of data to illustrate owners' ongoing issues with their own vehicles. It does not, however, capture the qualitative data that can help to (a) understand the cause of a problem, and (b) derive a solution to it. There is, therefore, considerable value to be gained from running an event such as the customer clinic, to gain a deeper understanding of issues highlighted by commercial surveys, through qualitative data capture and analysis. This event confirmed certain aspects of commercial survey results, investigated causes behind the issues, and took a more affective approach to understanding what premium SUV owner/drivers want from their seat adjustment controls. A large sample size and non-control specific questioning enabled a comprehensive high-level content analysis to be performed on preference-related factors, but was of limited value for exploration of specific controls and functions as sample size (and hence, confidence) drops off as the subject of analysis becomes more specific.

If confidence in the commercial survey data is high, participants in a subsequent customer clinic can be subjected to more specific questioning, giving higher sample sizes for function/control specific responses, but it should be noted that, occasionally, commercial survey sample sizes are small enough to cause confidence issues. Hence survey data should be examined in detail before a customer clinic methodology is defined.

Acknowledgement

This study was conducted as part of the HMI for Future Intelligent Vehicles research project, within the Innovative Manufacturing Research Centre (IMRC) at the University of Warwick. It is funded partially by the Engineering and Physical Sciences Research Council (EPSRC) and partially by our industrial collaborators, whom the authors would like to thank for their support.

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